

Monitoring Strategic Technologies using Open Research Information

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Context

Strategic technologies

- Closed sources
- Methodology not transparent
- Not replicable

Our contribution

Methodology (1)

Research questions

Collaboration with UNL

How does Dutch research contribute to the development of strategic technologies?

How does it compare internationally?

Topics -> technologies

Methodology (2)

Data

Source: [OpenAlex](#) — fully open bibliographic database

Coverage: Global output for relevant topics, 2019-2024

Results

Conclusions & discussion

Key findings

What the data show

Dutch universities are active contributors to most strategic technologies identified in national policy

Strength varies considerably across technologies — not a uniform picture

High shares in some areas (e.g. quantum, photonics); more modest in others (e.g. semiconductors)

Limitations & future work

Limitations

Assignment at topic level is very 'broad strokes'

Focus on academic publications; industry R&D is not captured

Next steps

Waiting for Broccoli...allows publication level assignment

How can RINN contribute

RI as methodology partners

Expertise in metadata important to operationalize policy concepts

Advocate for open research information in policy discussions

Bridge between research assessment and policy communities